

Face Mask and Changes in the Blood Oxygen Saturation of Theatre Workers at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Background: Facemasks provide some level of protection to theatre workers in case of fluid splash, and has become essential post-COVID. However, wearing facemasks during long procedures may lead to an increase in the level of CO₂ trapped beneath the mask, potentially decreasing the blood oxygen level. **Objective:** to investigate changes in the oxygen saturation levels of theatre workers at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital. **Materials and Methods:** quasi-experimental study involving healthy theatre workers. Data on demographic details, and medical and social history was collected using a proforma while the temperature and humidity of the theatre were measured, and values of oxygen saturation of each individual were collected using a pulse oximeter. **Results:** Overall mean SPO₂ of all theatre workers before surgery was 98.05 ± 0.85, which decreased significantly (p<0.05) 2 hours later (96.50±0.14) and then increased again. Significant decrease in SPO₂ level was observed for surgeries lasting 0-60 minutes and 2 hours later for surgeries lasting 121-180 minutes. SPO₂ level of theatre workers decreased significantly between 0.5 hours to 2 hours later in workers using surgical face masks. **Conclusion:** Changes in SPO₂ of theatre workers in the teaching hospital occur in short-duration surgeries and when the theatre workers have reached their stress threshold, likely between 2 hours and 2.5 hours into the surgery. Furthermore, the decrease in SPO₂ of theatre workers in this tertiary institution only occurs in those that use the surgical type of face mask.

Keywords: Face mask, SPO₂, Theatre workers, Surgeries, Duration of surgery..

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INTRODUCTION

The use of facemasks in surgical theatres dates back to Germany in the 19th century. [1] Theatre personnel use facemasks to prevent the transmission of nasal and oral pathogens from the surgical team to the surgical wound. This has been a standard practice in surgical procedures for over a century.[2] Recently, it has been recognized that facemasks offer some degree of protection to the surgeon in case of fluid splash. With the potential presence of SARS-COVID, the use of facemasks in theatres and other clinical settings has become an absolute necessity.[3]

It is generally accepted that theatre personnel have to wear facemasks during long procedures lasting four hours or more. Despite the universal air-conditioning standard in operating theatres, wearing facemasks for extended periods can result in physical discomfort, fatigue, headaches, deterioration of surgical judgement and performance, and a decrease in blood oxygenation. [4-5]

Normal blood oxygen saturation is typically defined as a fractional saturation of 90 to 97.5%, corresponding to an arterial oxygen partial pressure of 13.3 to 13.7 kPa. When using a facemask, the increased levels of CO₂ that become trapped beneath the mask can lead to a decrease in blood oxygen. [4-6] There have been reports linking the use of facemasks to decrease in saturated oxygen levels among surgical theatre workers. One study examining the effect of facemasks during major surgery found that they obstructed the inflow and outflow of air, resulting in low oxygen saturation and increased CO₂ concentration in the blood. [4] Similarly, another study found that healthy anesthesiologists wearing face masks for more than 2 hours experienced significantly decreased SPO₂ levels and increased respiratory rates without affecting heart rates. [7] Among oral surgeons, wearing an FFP2 covered by a surgical mask can induce a reduction in circulating oxygen concentration, an increase in heart rate, and a sensation of shortness of breath, lightheadedness, and headaches. [6] In another study, the effect of N95 mask usage on hypoxia among frontline dental health workers revealed a significant drop in oxygen

saturation after one hour of wearing the mask, which increased in the second hour. [8] An increase in nasal resistance with the use of N95 respirators and surgical facemasks has also been reported. [9]

The few studies that have been conducted on the effects of face masks on oxygen saturation in the blood among theatre workers suggest that there is not enough information available, both locally and internationally. The result of the study will be useful in resolving the ongoing controversy regarding the safety of facemasks, which can influence compliance to their use during times of epidemic or pandemic to prevent infections. There are no local studies in Nigeria and the few available studies have not yet reached a consensus. Moreover, most of the studies have been conducted on facemasks adapted to respirators, with almost no studies on ordinary surgical facemasks. Therefore, this study aims to further investigate the effects of facemasks on oxygen saturation before and after they are worn by theatre personnel in a tertiary health institution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

The study was a quasi-experimental study of before-after design.

Study Population

The study was carried out at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, which is located in Nnewi, a commercial center situated in South Eastern Nigeria. The hospital serves as a reference center in the region and conducts surgeries in almost all areas of medicine, such as Obstetrics & Gynecology, Neurosurgery, Otorhinolaryngology, Orthopedics, General Surgery, and Pediatric Surgery. Typically, the hospital performs around 65 surgeries every week, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the number has decreased. Each surgery session involves about 6 to 15 people, including the surgical team, anaesthetists, perioperative nurses, and students. All healthy theatre personnel who gave their consent were included. However, individuals with health co-morbidities such as asthma, sickle cell disease, chronic bronchitis, or cardiac disease were excluded. Each recruited participant spent at least 30 minutes in the theatre.

Sample size determination and sample size statement

Assuming a moderate standardized effect size of 0.3 and a level of confidence of 95%, we set the power at 80%. This means that there is an 80% chance of detecting an effect size of at least 0.3 or having a P value of less than 0.05, which would allow us to reject the null hypothesis. Since we do not have enough information from previous studies and cannot conduct a pilot study, we will use the following formula to determine the sample size for our paired group study design: $n = 2 \times \left(\frac{Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{\beta}}{d} \right)^2 = 2 \times \left(\frac{1.96 + 0.84}{0.3} \right)^2 = 174$

To account for attrition, using the formula total sample size (N_t) = $\frac{N}{1 - \text{attrition rate}}$, assuming attrition rate 20% (0.2), $N_t = \frac{174}{1 - 0.2} = \text{approx. } 218$

A sample size of 218 at a confidence level of 95% was used for the study.

Interventions: The study and control groups were individuals who served as a control to themselves and the Intervention was the use of pulse oxymeter to check the oxygen saturation (SpO₂) upon arrival, before a face mask is worn.

Outcome assessed: The SpO₂ was checked again after 30 minutes and continued at the same interval until the surgery was completed or the personnel left the theatre.

Data collection was done from 14th April 2021 to 13th April 2022 using a proforma designed to collect demographic details, medical, surgical and social history, the number of people in the operating suite, temperature and humidity of the theatre, and the values of oxygen saturation using a pulse oximeter, among others.

Ethical Considerations: Participants were enrolled voluntarily, with informed consent and anonymity guaranteed.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism. Categorical data were presented as percentages and proportions, while numeric data were presented as means and standard deviations. One-way ANOVA and Turkey multiple comparison test were used for statistical analysis. The data were presented using graphs and tables, and the statistical significance was set at a 95% confidence level.

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics of theatre workers

A total of 154 theatre workers consented to study at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital. The proportion of enrolled male and female theatre workers was 51.3% and 48.7%, respectively. Most theatre workers belonged to the 25-35 age group (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographics characteristics of study participants

Variable	Frequency n=154	Percent (%)
Age (years)		
25-35	108	70.1
36-45	37	24.0
46-55	6	3.9
56-65	3	2.0
Gender		
Female	74	48.7
Male	78	51.3
Highest education level		
Secondary	13	8.4
Tertiary	142	91.6
Religion		
Christianity	153	100.0

Table 2: The title of surgery observed

Title of surgery	Frequency (%)	Percent (%)
ELCS	13	8.6
EMCS	10	6.6
EUA+biopsy	3	2.0
EUA, staging and biopsy	8	5.3
Hysterectomy/myomectomy	1	0.7
Abdominal myomectomy	19	12.5
Adenotonsillectomy	3	2.0
Bilateral hydrocelectomy+bilateral Orchidectomy	2	1.3
Caesarean section	9	5.9
Cervical ceradage	3	2.0
Craniectomy	1	0.7
Excision biopsy	2	1.3
Fronto-parieto-temporal craniotomy	4	2.6
Herniorrhaphy	3	2.0
Hysterolaparoscopy+dye test	3	2.0
Hysteroscopic retrieval of IUCD	1	0.7
Modified wertherms hysterectomy	8	5.3
Myomectomy	17	11.2
Nasal reconstruction	9	5.9
Posterior saggital auorectoplasty	4	2.6
Repeat myomectomy	5	3.3
Total abdominal hysterectomy	4	2.6
Urethroplasty	4	2.6
Vaginal hysterectomy	6	4.0
Vaginoplasty	4	2.6
Wide local excision	6	4.0

Table 3: Overall mean SPO₂ levels of theatre workers at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital

Variable	Mean \pm SD	RANGE	Median (IQR)
SPO ₂ (before surgery %)	98.05 \pm 0.85	96 - 100	98 (98 - 99)
SPO ₂ (0.5hr. Later %)	97.62 \pm 1.02	92 - 99	98 (97 - 98)
SPO ₂ (1.0hr. Later %)	97.47 \pm 1.59	84 - 99	98 (97 - 98)
SPO ₂ (2.0hr. Later %)	96.50 \pm 10.14*	9 - 99	98 (97 - 98)
SPO ₂ (2.5hr. Later %)	97.87 \pm 0.71	96 - 99	98 (98.5 - 98)
SPO ₂ (3.0hr. Later %)	97.64 \pm 1.01	96 - 99	98 (97 - 98)

*overall mean SPO₂ significantly different from the overll mean SPO₂ before surgery

Figure 1: Types of face masks used at the Nnamdi Azikiwe Teaching Hospital

Figure 2: Change in oxygen saturation by duration of surgery. *SPO₂ level significantly different from the SPO₂ before surgery

Figure 3: Changes in oxygen saturation using different face masks

Title of Surgery conducted at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital during the study

During the study, 152 surgeries were performed at the teaching hospital including Elective Caesarean Section (ELCS), Emergency Caesarean Section (EMCS), Examination under Anaesthesia and biopsy (EUA+biopsy), abdominal myomectomy, excision biopsy, vaginoplasty, wide local excision etc. Among all the surgeries performed, laparotomic surgeries such as myomectomy and abdominal myomectomy accounted for 12.5% and 11.2%, respectively. This was followed by EMCS, elective caesarean section, caesarean sections and nasal reconstruction, as shown in Table 2.

Types of masks used by theatre workers at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital

At the teaching hospital and among theatre workers, the most commonly used facemasks were surgical masks, FFP-surgical masks, N95 masks, N95 masks with respirators, and cloth masks. Surgical masks accounted for the highest percentage of usage (81.03%) followed by N95 with respirators, as shown in Figure 1.

Overall mean SPO₂ of theatre workers at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital

The mean SPO₂ level of theatre workers before surgery was 98.05±0.85%. After 30 minutes and one hour of surgery, the mean SPO₂ level were 97.05±0.85% and 97.47±1.59% respectively. However, there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the SPO₂ level during these time frames compared to before surgery. After two hours, the overall mean SPO₂ level of theatre workers reduced significantly to 96.50±10.14% ($p<0.05$). However, after 2.5 hours and 3 hours, the SPO₂ level increased to 97.87±0.71% and 97.64±1.01% respectively but the difference from the before-surgery SPO₂ level was not significant ($p>0.05$), as shown in Table 3.

Change in oxygen saturation at different durations of surgery

During surgeries lasting between 0-60 minutes, the SPO₂ levels at 0.5hr and 1hr into the surgery were significantly lower ($p<0.05$) than the SPO₂ levels before the surgery. For surgeries lasting between 61-120 minutes, the SPO₂ levels at 0.5hr, 1hr, and 2hrs

into the surgery did not differ significantly ($p>0.05$) from the SPO₂ levels before the surgery. For surgeries lasting between 121-180 minutes, the SPO₂ levels remained statistically unchanged at 0.5hr and 1hr into the surgery, but after 2hrs and 2.5hrs of surgery, the SPO₂ levels decreased significantly. For surgeries lasting more than 180 minutes, the SPO₂ levels remained statistically unchanged throughout the surgery period (Figure 2).

Changes in oxygen saturation using different facemasks

Theatre workers who used cloth facemasks had a slight decrease in SPO₂ levels 0.5 hours after surgery, which remained the same 1 hour later. However, at 2hrs and 2.5hrs after surgery, the SPO₂ levels increased and returned to the same level as before surgery at 3hrs. There was no significant difference in SPO₂ levels of theatre workers who used cloth facemasks throughout the surgery. Two theatre workers used FFP-surgical masks, and their SPO₂ levels decreased slightly from before surgery to after surgery, but the sample size was too small to analyze. The SPO₂ levels of theatre workers who used N95 facemasks decreased 0.5 hours after surgery but then remained stable 1hr later. At 2 hours after surgery, the SPO₂ levels had increased slightly. There was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in SPO₂ levels of theatre workers who used N95 facemasks before surgery and during the different time intervals after surgery. Similarly, theatre workers who used N95 with respirator facemasks also had no significant difference ($p<0.05$) in SPO₂ levels comparing the before-surgery SPO₂ level and the different time durations SPO₂ values. However, theatre workers who wore surgical masks had a significant decrease ($p<0.05$) in SPO₂ levels 0.5 hours and 1 hour after surgery. At 2.5hrs and 3hrs later, the SPO₂ levels slightly increased but were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) from the level before surgery (Figure 3).

DISCUSSION

The study results revealed that laparotomy for gynaecological conditions were the most common surgeries conducted at the teaching hospital during the study period. The theatre workers' most commonly used facemask is the surgical facemask, followed by the N95 respirator. A decrease in the

overall mean SPO₂ of theatre workers occurs 2 hours after donning the facemask during surgery, after which it increases again. A decrease in SPO₂ of theatre workers occurs 0.5 hours and 1 hour later for surgeries lasting 0-60 minutes, and 2 hours and 2.5 hours later for surgeries lasting 121-180 minutes. Concerning the type of facemask, a decrease in SPO₂ was only observed in theatre workers who wore the surgical facemask 0.5 hours, 1 hour, and 2 hours later into surgery.

This study found that laparotomy for gynaecological conditions was the most frequently performed surgeries by theatre workers at the teaching hospital during the study period. This is similar to the findings from other studies in Nigeria. [10-11] Laparotomy involves making an open incision in the abdomen to access the abdominal cavity and examine organs. [12] It is used for emergency abdominal examinations, myomectomies, and C-sections. The high percentage of laparotomies in the study suggests that it is a standard procedure for managing critical conditions and can be provided by any hospital. The duration of laparotomy surgery varies from case to case due to differences in the indications, skill of surgeons and whether there is complication or not. The duration of laparotomy surgery indirectly determines the duration of use of facemask, therefore, may impact the SPO₂ levels and their fluctuations as was found in our study. [7] The implication is that theatre users who use facemasks and embark on long laparotomy surgeries are preinformed on what to expect regarding their SPO₂.

The surgical facemask, also known as a medical face mask, was the most commonly used facemask in the study. The high percentage of surgical facemask use may be due to its lower cost and greater availability compared to the N95 mask.[13] Additionally, the surgical facemask has a significantly higher filtration rate than the N95 respirator mask. [14] A similar result showing a high percentage of use of surgical facemasks has been reported among healthcare workers in a tertiary hospital in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.[13] The low percentage use of N95 respirator facemasks may be due to their discomfort, improper wearing, and the need for frequent adjustments.[15], and possibly its high cost.

In this study, the mean SPO₂ levels of theatre workers did not show a significant decrease until 2 hours into the surgery, after which it increased again. The notable drop in the overall mean SPO₂ levels at the 2-hour mark is believed to be due to operational stress.[16], and the subsequent increase at 2.5 hours and 3 hours may be attributed to the relief felt by the theatre workers at the success of the surgery, and partly due to systemic reaction to accumulated CO₂. [17] In a study involving 53 surgeons wearing surgical facemasks, their SPO₂ levels were observed to decrease after one hour and the decrease was attributed to operational stress.[4] In contrast, a study on the effects of surgical masks on the peripheral oxygen and respiratory rate of anaesthesiologists reported no significant difference within 2 hours of wearing the masks but observed a statistical decrease in SPO₂ levels after more than 2 hours.[7] This was attributed to the fact that anaesthesiologists who work in operating rooms and wear mask for long periods of time adapt to the psychological and physical effects caused by mask use. Additionally, the longterm stress of the anaesthesiologist can lead to reduced stress response of the cardiovascular system.[18]

This study reveals a significant decrease in SPO₂ level at 0.5hr and 1 hr later into the surgery for surgeries lasting between 0-60 minutes. This immediate drop may be attributed to a decrease in O₂ inhalation and an increased inhalation of exhaled CO₂ trapped within the breathing zone of the mask. [8] In a study using N95 masks, a similar result of a decrease in SPO₂ was reported after 1 hour of wearing an N95 mask. Surgeries lasting 61-120 minutes did not show a significant difference in SPO₂ levels, which aligns with a report on the use of surgical masks by Dental Healthcare workers in a nonclinical setting.[8] The decrease in SPO₂ levels at 2hrs and 2.5hrs later for surgeries lasting 121-180 minutes in this study may be attributed to operational stress. Generally, in this study, there were fluctuations in SPO₂ levels of theatre workers at different durations of surgery. A study where SPO₂ increased in some healthcare workers, remained unchanged in some and decreased in some has been reported.[19] A significant decrease in SPO₂ at 0.5hr, 1hr, and 2hrs later into surgery for theatre

workers donning the surgical facemask type may be attributed to psychological restriction over spontaneous breathing caused by wearing surgical face mask by the active theatre workers and operational stress experienced by the active doctors as opined by Beder et al.[4]

The strength of this study lies in the fact that the findings of this study can guide theatre workers with impaired SPO2 without facemasks to be cautious with the use of facemasks. However, it is limited by lack of robustness in the sample size, and its quasi-experimental design which may limit applicability in the general population.

CONCLUSION

The use of facemasks has been found to affect the oxygen saturation levels (SPO2) of theatre workers at Nnamdi Azikwe University Teaching Hospital during surgeries lasting between 0-60 minutes, and when they are under operational stress. Specifically, the use of surgical face masks can cause a decrease in SPO2 levels among theatre workers.

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Authors' contributions

ODN Conceptualized and designed the work, NDO, JEN, COA, CIE, CCO, FCO were involved in literature search, data collection, data analysis, statistical analysis, manuscript preparation, manuscript editing and manuscript review. The authors read, approved the final manuscript and agreed to be responsible for all aspect of the work.

Data Availability

The Data used to support the findings of this are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Institution's Ethics Committee, with Reference number: NAUTH/CS/VOL.14/VER 3/04/2021/018.

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